

Leadership and Prosocial Behaviour among Faculty Members in Public Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of leadership (self-sacrificial leadership, ethical leadership, and servant leadership) on prosocial behaviour among faculty members in public tertiary institutions. The study adopted a descriptive survey. The population was 10,895 faculty members. SPSS version 28.0.1 was employed for data screening, while the Pearson correlation coefficient was used for hypothesis testing. The findings reveal that self-sacrificial leadership exhibits a positive and statistically significant correlation with prosocial behaviour among employees. This suggests that leaders who prioritize the needs and interests of others over personal gain are more likely to inspire acts of cooperation, altruism, and voluntary assistance within the workplace. Also, the results of this study indicate that servant leadership exhibits a positive and statistically significant correlation with prosocial behaviour among employees. This suggests that leaders who prioritize the growth, well-being, and needs of their followers are more likely to inspire acts of altruism, cooperation, and voluntary assistance within the workplace. The study concludes that leadership styles that emphasise selflessness, service, and the prioritization of collective interests, such as servant and self-sacrificial leadership, are positively and significantly associated with behaviours that promote cooperation, altruism, and mutual support. It is recommended that institutions should organise regular leadership development programmes that emphasize servant and self-sacrificial leadership qualities. This can encourage leaders to prioritise the needs of others, fostering a culture of empathy, support, and cooperation among faculty members.

Keywords: Self-sacrificial leadership, ethical leadership, servant leadership, and prosocial behaviour.

Introduction

While antisocial behaviours are harmful, the same cannot be said of prosocial behaviour. A number of individual and contextual predictors of antisocial behaviours have been identified, including organizational injustice (Ambrose, Seabright, & Schminke, 2002), negative affectivity (Aquino, Grover, Bradfield, & Allen, 1999), psychological contract breach (Bordia, Restubog, & Tang, 2008), work stressors (Chen & Spector, 1992), abusive supervision, and so forth (Mitchell & Ambrose, 2007).

While prior research has increased our understanding of the negative consequences of antisocial behaviour (known as destructive deviance) within organizations; in recent years, there is a growing interest in prosocial behaviour (known as constructive deviance). The interest in prosocial behaviour has grown because such behaviours can play a significant role in creating positive organizational change (Luthans & Church, 2002; Robbins & Galperin, 2010).

Prosocial behaviour is defined as a social behaviour that benefits other people or society as a whole such as helping, sharing, donating, co-operating, volunteering, obeying the rules and conforming to socially accepted behaviours in an organization (Luthans & Church, 2002). Prosocial behaviours are helpful to relationships, communities, and society (Luthans & Church, 2002). There is a pressing research need to integrate the various leadership behaviours in the leadership literature. This will allow us to discern the effects of leadership on prosocial behaviours. Accordingly, the current research aims to examine how leadership affects followers' prosocial behaviours such as volunteering, donations, knowledge exchange, voice, helping, cooperation, obedience to rules and regulations.

The present research contributes to the leadership literature by delving deeper into the complex leadership behaviours which have been neglected in previous studies. Existing research lacks a clear consensus on the mechanisms through which leadership behaviours affect follower outcomes, which restricts our understanding of how leadership exerts its influences. By integrating two major theoretical perspectives (social learning and social exchange perspectives), the present research pinpoints the primary theoretical drivers underlying leadership impacts and reconcile the previously divergent views on how self-sacrificial leadership, servant leadership and ethical leadership affect followers' prosocial behaviour. Thus, this study facilitates a combination of theoretical perspectives and a unified framework, which provides an avenue to harmonize differing views and findings related to the dynamics of leadership behaviours in public tertiary institutions.

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The influence of effective leadership on positive work outcomes is often perceived as uniform, but the effects are actually more complex and nuanced (Conger, 1990; Judge, Piccolo, & Kosalka, 2009), suggesting the existence of a dark side of bright leadership (Cheong, Spain, Yammarino, & Yun, 2016; Tourish, 2013).

Even more interestingly, effective leadership may simultaneously display dual effects on different desirable outcomes, such that the same force promoting one positive behaviour could be associated with a decrease in other equally desirable behaviours (Li, Chiaburu, & Kirkman, 2017; Zhang, Liao, Li, & Colbert, 2020). One reason for this paradoxical effect is the inherent tension between different desirable outcomes that are driven by distinct mechanisms. For example, a recent study found that employees' motivation to work so as to support the family can simultaneously increase their productivity and inhibit creativity, since both characteristics are predicted by different psychological mechanisms (Zhang et al., 2020). Leadership is an integral part of organizational success. Whether an organization succeeds or not, it depends on the leaders and the directions they shape for the organization to follow. Leadership, as a research area and as a practical skill, encompasses the ability of an individual, group, or organization to lead, influence, or guide other individuals, teams, or entire organizations (Zhang et al., 2020). Leadership behaviour in many public tertiary institutions has been marred with anomalies, thereby hindering effective and efficient functioning of state-owned institutions in Nigeria. Hence, the need for the present study.

Conceptual Review

Prosocial behaviour

Prosocial behaviour or intent to benefit others is a social behaviour that benefits other people or society as a whole such as helping, sharing, donating, co-operating, volunteering, obeying the rules and conforming to socially accepted behaviours in an organization (Dovidio, Piliavin, Schroeder, & Penner, 2017).

Prosocial behaviour improves recipient well-being and group functioning and is associated with helper benefits such as meaning, belonging, and mental health (Dovidio et al., 2006; Akin, Dunn, & Norton, 2012). In organizations, prosocial acts underpin collaboration and performance,

overlapping with (but not identical to) organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Paine, & Bachrach, 2000).

Self-sacrificial leadership and prosocial behaviour

By definition, self-sacrificial leadership is other-focused, in that such leaders focus on team members' needs, invest extra efforts into the team, and help team members accomplish their goals (Choi & Mai-Dalton, 1998; De Cremer et al., 2009). According to social learning theory (Bandura, 1977), human actions are learned observationally through modeling, that is, by paying attention to and emulating the attitudes, values, and behaviours of attractive and credible models (Brown & Treviño, 2006). Leaders are considered as role models because they have high power and status. Moreover, leaders who demonstrate high morality are more likely to be perceived as credible role models (Brown et al., 2005).

It has long been advised that leaders should serve as role models for their followers, who lead from the frontlines by devoting time and energy to pursuing collective goals (Hogan & Kaiser, 2005; Hoogervorst, De Cremer, van Dijke, & Mayer, 2012). One effective way for leaders to promote this outcome is to adopt self-sacrificial leadership, which requires leaders to set an example by going first, being willing to forgo self-interest to improve their team's welfare, voluntarily choosing difficult and risky tasks, and taking on extra responsibilities (Choi & Mai-Dalton, 1998; van Knippenberg & van Knippenberg, 2005).

In the present study, we suggest that self-sacrificial leadership may activate team members' different psychological mechanisms, thereby creating paradoxical effects for desirable team outcomes. According to social learning theory, team members often regard team leaders with formal power and morality as role models, and pay attention to and emulate behaviors from such credible role models (Bandura, 1973; Brown, Treviño, & Harrison, 2005). Through the observation process, team members will learn from self-sacrificing leaders to focus on others' interests and needs, resulting in more collective prosocial behaviour.

To advance research on self-sacrificial leadership, we draw on social learning theory (Bandura, 1977) to explore how self-sacrificial leadership differentially influences positive behaviours among faculty members. We focus on the effect of self-sacrificial leadership on the team members' behaviour level for three reasons. First, according to social learning theory, self-sacrificing leaders stand high in a prestige hierarchy (Bandura, 1986), which allows them to serve as salient role

models for the entire team. Second, public tertiary institutions are increasingly relying on teams to perform tasks, and leaders are often judged by the effectiveness and efficiency of the institution they lead (Mathieu, Gallagher, Domingo, & Klock, 2019). Finally, despite the importance of examining self-sacrificial leadership on members' behaviour, most previous research focused on the commonest leadership styles such as transformational, transactional, and laissez faire leadership styles (De Cremer et al., 2009; Mostafa & Bottomley, 2020). Thus, we examine how self-sacrificial leadership can shape prosocial behaviours in public tertiary institutions by formulating the hypothesis below:

H1: There is no significant relationship between self-sacrificial leadership and prosocial behaviour among faculty members in public tertiary institutions

Ethical leadership and prosocial behaviour

Ethical leadership is leadership that is directed by respect for ethical beliefs and values and for the dignity and rights of others. It is thus related to concepts such as trust, honesty, consideration, charisma, and fairness (Balwant, 2016). We propose that these behavioural attributes may promote employees' prosocial behaviours.

Research consistently finds a positive correlation between ethical leadership and prosocial behaviour. For example, Mayer et al. (2009) found that ethical leadership predicted increased helping behaviour among employees through enhanced moral identity. Similarly, Avey, Wernsing, and Palanski (2012) reported that ethical leaders cultivate a moral climate that encourages discretionary behaviours such as altruism, courtesy, and civic virtue. Grant and Mayer (2009) also showed that ethical leadership motivates prosocial actions both toward individuals (helping co-workers) and toward the organization (volunteering for extra tasks).

Ethical leadership fosters prosocial behaviour by shaping employees' moral reasoning, enhancing trust, and reinforcing prosocial norms (Mayer et al., 2009; Den Hartog & De Hoogh, 2009). Through role modelling, ethical leaders demonstrate behaviours that followers perceive as worthy of imitation, which encourages similar conduct (Bandura, 1986). Furthermore, ethical leaders create an environment of fairness and psychological safety, making employees more willing to engage in discretionary helping behaviours (Walumbwa et al., 2011).

Social learning theory (Bandura, 1986) provides a foundational explanation for this relationship—followers learn ethical and prosocial norms by observing leaders' conduct and the reinforcement of such behaviour. Additionally, social exchange theory (Blau, 1964) suggests that when employees perceive fairness and moral integrity from leaders, they reciprocate through extra-role prosocial acts that benefit the organization.

This conceptual linkage suggests that in public tertiary institutions, where collaboration, mentorship, and community service are vital, ethical leadership can significantly strengthen the frequency and quality of prosocial acts among faculty members. Based on the foregoing, the following hypothesis emerged:

H2: Ethical leadership has no correlation to prosocial behaviour among faculty members in public tertiary institutions

Servant leadership and prosocial behaviour

Servant leadership is a leadership philosophy in which the goal of the leader is to serve. This is different from traditional leadership where the leader's main focus is the thriving of their organization. A servant leader shares power, puts the needs of the employees first and helps people develop and perform as highly as possible. Instead of the people working to serve the leader, the leader exists to serve the people. As stated by its founder, Robert K. Greenleaf in 1977, a servant leader should be focused on "Do those served grow as persons? Do they, while being served, become healthier, wiser, freer, more autonomous, more likely themselves to become servants?"

Empirically, Hunter et al. (2013) found that servant leadership predicted follower helping behaviour by enhancing moral identity and commitment to others. Also, Liden et al. (2014) reported that servant leadership promotes community citizenship behaviours, as followers are more inclined to contribute to others' well-being when they perceive leaders as genuinely selfless. Similarly, Newman et al. (2017) demonstrated that servant leaders foster psychological safety and trust, which reduce interpersonal barriers to prosocial engagement in teams.

When leaders shift their mindset and serve first, they benefit because as employees acquire personal growth, the organization grows as well due to the employees' growing commitment and

engagement. In public tertiary institutions, servant leadership is particularly relevant because academic environments thrive on collaboration, mentorship, and community service. Faculty members who experience servant leadership are more likely to mentor junior colleagues and students, volunteer for institutional projects, and engage in activities that enhance collective academic and social outcomes. On the bases of existing literature and theoretical perspectives, the following hypothesis surfaced:

H3: There is no significant relationship between servant leadership and prosocial behaviour among faculty members in public tertiary institutions

Theoretical review

Self-sacrificial leadership, servant leadership and ethical leadership predominately draws on two social theories to explain how each influences followers' behaviour. The theories are social learning (Bandura, 1977, 1986) and social exchange theory (Blau, 1964). In servant leadership literature, the use of social learning theory argues that servant leaders are influencing their followers, as their followers observe and emulate the leader's positive behaviours. In contrast, social exchange theory is used to argue that a servant leader's followers are exhibiting positive behaviours due to the reciprocal relationship they develop with their leaders.

Methods

Study area

This study will focus on the faculty members in public Polytechnics located in North Central Nigeria. The zone consists of Benue, Nasarawa, Kwara, Kogi, Plateau, and Niger states.

Population/subjects

The twelve public Polytechnics spread across the 6 states that make up the North Central zone are the focus of the present study. The entire population of faculty members in these 12 institutions is 10,895. Based on Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size determination table, the minimum sample required for a population of 10,895 is 370. However, to give room for non-returned questionnaire and invalid questionnaires, the researcher administered 420 questionnaire.

Instrumentation

Prosocial Behaviour Questionnaire developed by Weir and Duveen (1981) was adapted to measure prosocial behaviours in the present study. Self-sacrificial leadership scale by De Cremer and van Knippenberg (2004) was adopted to measure self-sacrificial leadership. The most widely used measurement scale for Ethical Leadership is the Ethical Leadership Scale (ELS) developed by Brown, Treviño, and Harrison (2005). This scale has been highly influential in both academic research and organizational assessments. Lastly, the short form of servant leadership questionnaire by Liden et al. (2015) was adopted to measure servant leadership.

Results

Reliability Test

The reliability analysis presented in Table 1 was carried out using Cronbach's alpha, a measure that evaluates the internal consistency of the items used to assess each study variable. Cronbach's alpha values range between 0 and 1, with higher values signifying greater reliability of the measurement scale.

Table 1

Reliability Test

S/N	Variable	Scale reliability coefficient
1	Self-sacrificial Leadership	.888
2	Ethical Leadership	.712
3	Servant Leadership	.876
4	Prosocial Behaviour	.724

Source: Field survey, 2025

Using Cronbach's alpha, the reliability results in Table 1, show that all the study variables exceed the 0.50 benchmark to prove internal consistency. Hence, the study retained items with a minimum loading of 0.70 (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2017). Self-sacrificial leadership recorded the highest reliability coefficient at 0.888, reflecting excellent consistency among its measurement items. Servant leadership followed with a coefficient of 0.876, also demonstrating a high level of reliability. Prosocial behaviour achieved a coefficient of 0.724, which surpasses the benchmark and signifies satisfactory internal consistency among its items.

Ethical leadership, with a coefficient of 0.712, was the lowest among the variables but still above the 0.50 threshold, suggesting that its items possess adequate internal consistency for inclusion in the study. Overall, the results confirm that all four constructs i.e. self-sacrificial leadership, ethical leadership, servant leadership, and prosocial behaviour meet the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion, ensuring the suitability of the measurement scales for further analysis.

Multicollinearity Test

The study further performed a multicollinearity assessment to examine the presence of collinearity among the independent variables. The results, shown in Table 2, were derived using two main indicators: Tolerance and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Multicollinearity arises when independent variables exhibit a high degree of correlation with each other, potentially affecting the accuracy of regression analysis outcomes. According to Hair et al. (2010), a Tolerance value less than 0.1 or a VIF value exceeding 10 signals a possible multicollinearity concern.

Table 2

Collinearity Statistics

		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Self-sacrificial Leadership	.966	1.035
	Ethical Leadership	.966	1.036
	Servant Leadership	.934	1.071

a. Dependent Variable: Prosocial Behaviour

The collinearity statistics in Table 2 indicate that all independent variables in the model (self-sacrificial leadership, ethical leadership, and servant leadership) fall well within the acceptable limits suggested by Hair et al. (2010, 2017). Tolerance values range from 0.934 to 0.966, which are far above the critical threshold of 0.1, suggesting a low degree of shared variance among the predictors. Similarly, the corresponding VIF values range from 1.035 to 1.071, which are significantly below the cut-off value of 10, further confirming the absence of multicollinearity concerns.

These results imply that the independent variables are sufficiently distinct and do not exhibit problematic intercorrelations that could bias the regression estimates. Consequently, self-sacrificial leadership, ethical leadership, and servant leadership can be reliably included in the

regression model to predict prosocial behaviour without the risk of inflated standard errors or compromised statistical validity.

Model Fit

The result of the model fit is presented in table 3.

Table 3.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.264 ^a	.070	.062	2.22224	2.033

a. Predictors: (Constant), Servant Leadership, Self-sacrificial Leadership, Ethical Leadership

b. Dependent Variable: Prosocial Behaviour

The model summary in Table 3 shows that the predictors - self-sacrificial leadership, ethical leadership, and servant leadership - collectively have a weak positive relationship with prosocial behaviour, as indicated by the R value of 0.264. The R Square value of 0.070 reveals that only 7% of the variation in prosocial behaviour is explained by the independent variables, while the remaining 93% is attributable to other factors not included in the model. The adjusted R Square, which accounts for the number of predictors, is slightly lower at 0.062, indicating a marginal reduction in explanatory power when adjusting for model complexity.

The standard error of the estimate is 2.22224, reflecting the average distance between the observed and predicted values of prosocial behaviour. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.033 falls within the acceptable range of approximately 1.5 to 2.5, suggesting no significant autocorrelation in the residuals. Overall, while the model meets the statistical assumption of independent errors, its explanatory power is relatively low, implying that other unexamined factors may play a more substantial role in influencing prosocial behaviour.

ANOVA Test

The table 4 shows the output of the ANOVA test conducted for the study.

Table 4

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	139.985	3	46.662	9.449	.000 ^b
	Residual	1866.699	378	4.938		
	Total	2006.683	381			

a. Dependent Variable: Prosocial Behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Servant Leadership, Self-sacrificial Leadership, Ethical Leadership

The ANOVA results in Table 4 indicate that the regression model is statistically significant in explaining variations in prosocial behaviour. The regression sum of squares is 139.985, with a mean square of 46.662, producing an F-statistic of 9.449 and a corresponding significance value ($p = 0.000$), which is well below the 0.05 threshold. This confirms that the combined effect of self-sacrificial leadership, ethical leadership, and servant leadership has a statistically significant impact on prosocial behaviour.

The residual sum of squares is 1866.699, indicating the portion of variation in prosocial behaviour not explained by the model. The total sum of squares is 2006.683, meaning that the independent variables account for a modest proportion of the overall variation. Despite the relatively low R Square value observed in the model summary, the ANOVA results show that the predictors, when considered together, significantly contribute to explaining differences in prosocial behaviour among the respondents.

Test of Hypotheses

The purpose of the study was to investigate the relationships between the exogenous predictors - self-sacrificial leadership, ethical leadership, and servant leadership—and the endogenous variable, prosocial behaviour. To accomplish this, a Pearson two-tailed correlation analysis was conducted to assess both the direction and strength of the associations among these constructs. The results of this analysis are displayed in Table 5.

Table 5
Correlations

		Prosocial Behaviour
Self-sacrificial Leadership	Pearson Correlation	.198**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	382
Ethical Leadership	Pearson Correlation	-.048
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.345
	N	382
Servant Leadership	Pearson Correlation	.187**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	382
Prosocial Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	382

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion of results

The correlation results in Table 5 provide evidence to evaluate the stated hypotheses. For the first hypothesis, self-sacrificial leadership shows a positive and statistically significant correlation with prosocial behaviour ($r = 0.198$, $p = 0.000$). Since the p-value is below the 0.01 significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that self-sacrificial leadership significantly influences prosocial behaviour among faculty members.

The findings of this study reveal that self-sacrificial leadership exhibits a positive and statistically significant correlation with prosocial behaviour among employees. This suggests that leaders who prioritize the needs and interests of others over personal gain are more likely to inspire acts of cooperation, altruism, and voluntary assistance within the workplace. This aligns with Choi and Mai-Dalton (1999), who argue that self-sacrificial leaders foster trust and moral commitment, thereby encouraging employees to act in ways that benefit others. Similarly, De Cremer and van

Knippenberg (2005) found that leader self-sacrifice enhances group identification, which in turn promotes prosocial behaviour among followers.

The positive relationship found in this study also supports the assertion of Van Knippenberg and Van Knippenberg (2005) that when leaders demonstrate selflessness, employees perceive them as more authentic and ethical, motivating them to reciprocate through helping behaviours and greater interpersonal cooperation. These results highlight the critical role of self-sacrificial leadership in shaping a prosocial organizational culture.

Regarding the second hypothesis, ethical leadership demonstrates a weak negative and statistically insignificant relationship with prosocial behaviour ($r = -0.048$, $p = 0.345$). As the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained, suggesting that there is no meaningful relationship between ethical leadership and prosocial behaviour in this context.

For the third hypothesis, servant leadership exhibits a positive and statistically significant correlation with prosocial behaviour ($r = 0.187$, $p = 0.000$). With the p-value below the 0.01 threshold, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that servant leadership has a significant effect on prosocial behaviour among faculty members.

The results of this study indicate that servant leadership exhibits a positive and statistically significant correlation with prosocial behaviour among employees. This suggests that leaders who prioritize the growth, well-being, and needs of their followers are more likely to inspire acts of altruism, cooperation, and voluntary assistance within the workplace. According to Greenleaf (1977), servant leaders place service above self-interest, which fosters a culture of empathy and support, thereby encouraging followers to engage in behaviours that benefit others.

These findings align with the work of Liden, Wayne, Zhao, and Henderson (2008), who found that servant leadership promotes trust, moral responsibility, and commitment among employees, all of which are antecedents of prosocial behaviour. Similarly, Hunter et al. (2013) assert that servant leaders act as role models for ethical conduct, motivating subordinates to reciprocate through helping behaviours and organizational citizenship activities.

Furthermore, Ehrhart (2004) highlights that servant leadership's emphasis on empowerment and community building enhances group cohesion, which in turn encourages employees to go beyond

their formal job roles to assist colleagues and contribute to organizational goals. The significant positive relationship in the present study reinforces the idea that servant leadership not only benefits leader–follower relationships but also fosters a prosocial organizational climate.

Conclusion

This study establishes that leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping prosocial behaviour among faculty members in public tertiary institutions. The findings demonstrate that leadership styles that emphasize selflessness, service, and the prioritization of collective interests such as servant and self-sacrificial leadership are positively and significantly associated with behaviours that promote cooperation, altruism, and mutual support. Such behaviours are essential for fostering collegiality, enhancing teamwork, and creating a supportive academic environment that benefits both staff and students. In the context of public tertiary institutions, where resource constraints and diverse stakeholder needs often pose challenges, leaders who model ethical conduct, empathy, and commitment to others' growth can inspire faculty members to go beyond formal job requirements in contributing to institutional goals. Therefore, fostering leadership approaches that nurture prosocial behaviour is not only beneficial for organizational climate but also vital for improving institutional performance and academic excellence.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations emerged:

Promote servant leadership training: Institutions should organize regular leadership development programs that emphasize servant and self-sacrificial leadership qualities. This can encourage leaders to prioritize the needs of others, fostering a culture of empathy, support, and cooperation among faculty members.

Institutionalize prosocial behaviour recognition strategy: Management should implement formal recognition and reward systems for faculty members who demonstrate prosocial behaviours such as mentoring colleagues, volunteering for institutional tasks, or supporting community projects.

Integrate prosocial behaviour into performance appraisals: Faculty appraisal systems should incorporate indicators of prosocial behaviour such as teamwork, collaborative research, and peer support so that these contributions are recognized alongside teaching and research output.

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